

National Aeronautics and Space Administration

HELIOPHYSICS TECHNOLOGY ANNUAL REPORT

2024
HELIOPHYSICS BIG YEAR

HEST
HELIOPHYSICS STRATEGIC TECHNOLOGY OFFICE

The logo for the Heliophysics Strategic Technology Office (HEST) features the word "HEST" in a bold, white, sans-serif font. To the right of the text is a stylized graphic consisting of a blue and orange flame-like shape that curves into a blue circle with three white dots extending to the right, resembling a circuit board or data stream.

HESTO LEADERSHIP

Roshanak Hakimzadeh

Dr. Hakimzadeh is a Program Scientist and the Deputy Chief Technologist in the Heliophysics Division (HPD) at NASA Headquarters. In this role, she led the establishment of the Heliophysics Technology Program and the Heliophysics Strategic Technology Office (HESTO). Prior to joining HPD, she had a long and successful career at NASA's Glenn Research Center (GRC), where she led research and technology at the Branch, Division, and Directorate levels. Of note are her roles as GRC's Chief Technologist and Deputy Chief Technologist, where she provided technical leadership within GRC for the planning, management, and evaluation of a comprehensive, advanced, Center-wide technology development program to meet GRC's future mission responsibilities.

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Kyle McAllen

Mr. McAllen is the Program Manager for HESTO, a NASA Level II program based out of NASA's Wallops Flight Facility that supports the NASA Headquarters Heliophysics Technology Program. He previously was the Launch and Test Director at NASA's WFF, leading ISS Commercial Resupply, National Reconnaissance Office Orbital, DoD Testing and Evaluation, Navy Fleet Forces Training Exercises, and Sounding Rocket suborbital science missions out of Wallops Island, Virginia and Poker Flats, Alaska. He has also served on the Range Commanders Council Range Operations Group, National Rocket Propulsion Test Management Group, and NASA's Rocket Propulsion Test Management Board.

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Steven Christe

Dr. Christe is a Research Astrophysicist in the Heliophysics division at NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center. His background and interests have focused on the science of impulsive energy release on the Sun, such as solar flares. He has worked on multiple sounding rocket launches (FOXSI) and a balloon mission (HEROES), which have matured X-ray detectors and grazing-incidence focusing optics. Dr. Christe was the Principal Investigator for the FOXSI Small Explorer mission concept, which was selected for a Phase A study, and is currently leading the development of an X-ray detector for the PADRE H-FORT mission.

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Eliad Peretz

Dr. Peretz is HESTO deputy lead scientist and a mission and instrument scientist in the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center Heliophysics Division. He's led research and technology at the Branch and Division level at GSFC, served as Deputy PI for the Landolt mission, PM for the Measuring Directivity to Determine Electron Anisotropy (MeDDEA) instrument on PoLARization Directivity X-Ray Experiment (PADRE) and X-ray attenuators to study solar flares on Focusing Optics X-ray Solar Imager (FOXSI) 4. He's also worked on UV spectrometer development to study the lunar exosphere and was a former small-sat development lab lead. He has been awarded NASA's Exceptional Achievement Medal, Exceptional Engineering Achievement Medal, Early Career Achievement Medal, Robert H. Goddard Award, and NASA's Early Career Excellence award.

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Melissa Cold

Ms. Cold serves as the Program Specialist for HESTO through NASA's Wallops Flight Facility Small Satellite and Special Projects Office (S3PO). She works closely with the NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD) Program Officers in the oversight of grants, cooperative agreements, and technology awards. She also serves in a similar capacity for other programs across Heliophysics and Astrophysics, including the H-FORT, Pioneers, and APRA programs. Throughout her NASA career, Melissa has supported multiple organizations across WFF in a resource management capacity and NASA Kennedy Space Center as the Lead Resource Analyst for the Exploration Research and Technology Program.

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Chantayle Barber

Ms. Barber is the HESTO Grants Manager, overseeing Heliophysics Division Technology Program grant funding for all HESTO-managed projects. She assists awarded PIs with grant management and supervises all HESTO grants, cooperative agreements, Inter Agency Agreements, and Research and Technology Operating Plans. She also serves as HESTO's financial point of contact with NASA Heliophysics Division stakeholders, interfacing with the S3PO Program, NASA Shared Services Center, and HQ Inter-Agency Agreements Office. She previously managed grants for NASA's Earth Science Division and served as a budget and procurement executive in the Office of the Deputy Mayor for Health and Human Services, District of Columbia.

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WELCOME

I am thrilled to present our 2024 Heliophysics Technology Annual Report, showcasing HESTO's pivotal investments in advancing Heliophysics technology. This report includes the results of our Heliophysics Technology and Instrument Development for Science (H-TIDeS) and Heliophysics Flight Opportunities Studies (H-FOS) programs. I am also pleased to introduce the recipients of our 2024 awards, who will begin their work of discovery in 2025.

Over the past year, we've achieved major milestones. We have maintained a robust portfolio and have grown our community of technologists. We've increased mission infusions, expanded our portfolio of technologies to include those developed through the suborbital program, and launched the Heliophysics Technology Analysis Group (H-TPAG) to broaden community engagement. Our second annual HELIOTECH2024 Heliophysics Technology Symposium was a great success, and we're pleased to have selected our first Pathfinder flight project.

Looking ahead, the newly-released 2024 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics will guide our technology investment priorities, propelling innovation that enables new scientific breakthroughs. With HESTO soon to be fully staffed, we are poised to increase collaboration and purposeful technology infusion. We're also actively seeking new rideshare opportunities to further mature technologies and advance Heliophysics research.

Thank you for your dedication to pushing the frontiers of Heliophysics!

Roshanak
Roshanak Hakimzadeh, PhD
HESTO Program Scientist

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PORTFOLIO OVERVIEW

The technology portfolio is ROSES elements B.8 Heliophysics Instrument Development for Science (H-TIDeS) and B.10 Heliophysics Flight Opportunity Studies (H-FOS).

H-TIDeS

ITD

LNAPP

H-TIDeS includes the Laboratory Nuclear, Atomic, and Plasma Physics (LNAPP) and Instrument Technology Development (ITD) focus areas. LNAPP supports studies that probe fundamental physical processes and produce measurements that support spacecraft observations and models. ITD includes innovative instrument and technology developments for future space flight opportunities.

H-FOS

H-FOS supports Heliophysics science mission concept studies at the pre-Phase A level.

● HELIOSPHERE ●

● ITM ●

● MAGNETOSPHERE ●

● SOLAR SCIENCE ●

● INTERDISCIPLINARY ●

HESTO is pleased to announce its 2024 selections:

2024

- **Line Survey and Density Sensitivity Studies in Support of Hinode, MUSE, and Solar-C**
PI: Daniel Savin, Columbia University 24-HTIDS24-0002 Use the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory electron beam ion trap to measure key atomic data used to analyze solar EUV spectra (e.g., Ca XV density diagnostic line ratios), perform a high-resolution Fe X line survey in the ~170-290 Å bandpass, and survey O, Ne, Al, Si, S, Mg, Fe, and Ni lines in the 284 and 171 Å bandpass of SDO AIA.
- **Laboratory Study of Asymmetric Reconnection Including Diamagnetic Suppression**
PI: Jan Egedal, University of Wisconsin, Madison 24-HTIDS24-0003 Use the Terrestrial Reconnection EXperiment (TRES) to measure the 3D electrostatic and magnetic structures of the reconnection region for parameter ranges including large plasma beta, density asymmetry, and a guide magnetic field to understand reconnection in the magnetosphere.
- **Next-Generation Solar Neutron Tracking (SONTRAC) Instrument**
PI: Georgia de Nolfo, NASA's GSFC 24-HTIDS24-0005 Complete development of Solar Neutron TRACKing (SONTRAC), a fully-integrated neutron spectrometer that consists of plastic-scintillator fiber bundles read out by commercially available high-resolution, fine-grain silicon photomultipliers to measure neutrons from solar eruptive events.
- **Shuttered Plasma Instrument for Detecting Environmental Response (SPIDER)**
PI: Shawn Liang, JHU/APL 24-HTIDS24-0006 Develop the Shuttered Plasma Instrument for Detecting Environmental Response (SPIDER) to detect 10 eV - 5 keV ions with the resolution needed to distinguish outflowing N⁺ from O⁺, a key measurement for the study of magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling.
- **High-Rate X-ray Spectrometer for Solar and Space Physics**
PI: Lindsay Glesener, University of Minnesota 24-HTIDS24-0022 Develop a new compact, low-resource, fast hard X-ray detector to accurately monitor the high fluxes from solar flares on the Sun. It uses scintillator crystals coupled with Silicon Photomultipliers and custom electronics to support 2 million counts per second, which are expected from the largest flares.
- **Development of next generation compact time-of-flight plasma instruments for Heliophysics exploration**
PI: Jorg-Micha Jahn, Southwest Research Institute 24-HTIDS24-0025 Develop New Time-Of-Flight (NTOF), a new compact top hat electrostatic analyzer. This time-of-flight ion spectrometer replaces carbon foils with micropore optics and graphene foils, reducing the need for high voltage power supplies.
- **A high geometric factor, 3D-Cylindrical And Tiny Spectrometer (3D-CATS) for fast plasma measurements on future missions**
PI: Dhirendra Kataria, Southwest Research Institute 24-HTIDS24-0039 Develop 3D-Cylindrical And Tiny Spectrometer (3D-CATS), which will provide ion or electron velocity distribution functions covering a large fraction of the sky at high time resolution to determine bulk plasma moments with accuracies comparable to current state-of-the-art space plasma sensors (e.g., FPI on MMS), with lower mass and power requirements.
- **The Scotopic Solar Activity X-ray Imager SmallSat (SSAXI-SmallSat)**
PI: Chris Moore, Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory 24-HFOS24-0008 Study the SSAXI-SmallSat solar mission concept that plans to measure low intensity, soft X-ray emission from the solar corona and provide better understand about the heating processes present in active regions and the quiet Sun.
- **Ultraviolet Imaging of Earth's Auroral Oval from a Cubesat**
PI: Greg Holsclaw, University of Colorado, Boulder 24-HFOS24-0013 Study the Cubesat for Auroral Magnetosphere of Earth Observations (CAMEO) mission concept. CAMEO is a high-altitude, multi-wavelength, far-ultraviolet Earth auroral imaging mission to understand the dynamics and coupling of Earth's magnetosphere, ionosphere, and atmosphere and their response to solar and terrestrial inputs.

2023

- **Laboratory XUV Spectroscopy: Increasing the Scientific Return of Solar Missions** PI: Amy Gall, SAO 23-HTIDS23-0008
- **Study of electron acceleration during magnetic reconnection by soft x-ray tomography** PI: Jongsoo Yoo, Princeton University 23-HTIDS23-00011
- **Hybrid AC/DC Magnetometer with Attitude Determination and Control System** PI: Mark Moldwin, University of Michigan 23-HTIDS23-0001
- **Optics for Compact Two-dimensional Energetic Atom (OCTEA)** PI: Jerry Goldstein, Southwest Research Institute 23-HTIDS23-0004
- **Development of the Suprathermal Particle and Relativistic Electron Magnetic Spectrometer (SuPREMeS)** PI: Drew Turner, JHU/APL 23-HTIDS23-00012
- **Scanning Coronal and Heliospheric Imager (SCHI)** PI: Juliana Vievering, JHU/APL 23-HTIDS23-0016
- **A Miniature Solar Wind Sensor (MSWIS) for future low-cost, constellation, and deep-space missions** PI: Keiichi Ogasawara, Southwest Research Institute 23-HTIDS23-0017
- **A Spaceborne Vacuum Ultraviolet (VUV) Fourier Transform Spectrometer (FTS)** PI: Ed Thiemann, University of Colorado, Boulder [LASP] 23-HTIDS23-0022
- **Development and Testing of a Multi-Needle Langmuir Probe for the Detection of Extremely Small Spatial Structures in Low Earth Orbit** PI: Aroh Barjatya, Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University 23-HTIDS23-0023
- **A New HOPE for Ionospheric Outflow and Cold Magnetospheric Plasma Measurements** PI: Carlos Maldonado, LLNL 23-HTIDS23-0024
- **Multi-detector Experiment for next-Generation Applications in Heliophysics (MEGA-H)** PI: Joshua Eskin, Ball Aerospace 23-HTIDS23-0025
- **CubeSat: On the Radiation belt electron Acceleration (CORA)** PI: Hong Zhao, Auburn University 23-HFOS23-0003

2022

- **Production Pathways of the OH Meinel Band Emission Required for TIMED/SABER Observations** PI: Konstantinos Kalogerakis, SRI International 22-HTIDS22-0008
- **Scaling Studies of Seeded Alfvén Wave Parametric Decay Instability in the Laboratory** PI: Feiyu Li, New Mexico Consortium 22-HTIDS22-0019
- **Goddard Miniature Coronagraph** PI: Jeffrey Newmark, NASA's GSFC 22-HTIDS22-0004
- **Solar Neutron TRACKing Instrument (SONTRAC) Follow-on** PI: Georgia de Nolfo, NASA's GSFC 22-HTIDS22-0005
- **Lightsheet Anomaly Resolution And Debris Observation-Neuromorphic (LARSDO-N)** PI: Andrew Nicholas, NRL 22-HTIDS22-0006 interdisciplinary
- **HIRSL: a High-Resolution Spectrograph in Lyman alpha** PI: Majd Mayyasi, Boston University 22-HTIDS22-0007
- **Measuring Plasma Parameters and Waves in the Ionosphere of Earth** PI: Mihailo Martinovic, University of Arizona, Tucson 22-HTIDS22-0013
- **Debris and meteoroid ENvironment Sensor (DENTS): Instrument Technology Development** PI: David Malaspina, University of Colorado, Boulder 22-HTIDS22-0014 interdisciplinary
- **Development and Testing of a Miniaturized Double Langmuir Probe for Small-satellite Platforms** PI: Robert Clayton, Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University 22-HTIDS22-0018
- **Space Debris Detection and Characterization Using an in-situ LIDAR Sensor Platform** PI: John McVey, Aerospace Corp 22-HTIDS22-0020
- **Miniaturized Charging Mitigation Shell Instrument for Magnetospheric Cold Plasma Sensors** PI: Justin Lee, Aerospace Corp 22-HTIDS22-0023
- **Satellite Space Weather Investigation Frontier (SWIFT)** PI: Mojtaba Akhavan-Tafti, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor 22-HFOS22-0001
- **Space Weather Impact on Planetary Emissions (SWIPE)** PI: Mary Knapp, MIT 22-HFOS22-0002 interdisciplinary
- **Satellite Auroral Plasma Sounders (SAPS)** PI: Alex Chartier, Johns Hopkins University 22-HFOS22-0003
- **Loss Through Auroral Microburst Pulsations Satellite (LAMPsat) Flight Opportunity Study** PI: Mykhaylo Shumko, JHU/APL 22-HFOS22-0007

PORTFOLIO OVERVIEW

2021

- **Exploring 3D Collisionless Magnetic Reconnection in the Laboratory** PI: Jan Egedal, University of Wisconsin, Madison 21-HTIDS21-0003
- **Development of Grotifer: a CubeSat for Three-dimensional Electric Field Measurements** PI: Solène Lejosne, University of California, Berkeley 21-HTIDS21-0002
- **High-Frequency Magnetic Loop for Heliophysics Exploration** PI: Xiaojia Zhang, University of California, Los Angeles 21-HTIDS21-0004
- **An Imaging Polarimeter for Hydrogen Lyman- α** PI: Sam Tun Beltran, NRL 21-HTIDS21-0010
- **Low-resource Instrumentation for Scientific Measurements in Planetary Thermospheres** PI: James Clemmons, University of New Hampshire 21-HTIDS21-0012
- **Dual Cluster Mission Concept Study** PI: Xinlin Li, University of Colorado, Boulder 21-HFOS21-0001
- **LabOratory for the Behavior of the SloT Region (LOBSTR)** PI: Rachael Filwett, Univ of Iowa 21-HFOS21-0002

2020

- **Study of Coronal X-ray Jet Formation Using Advanced Numerical Simulations and Laboratory Experiments** PI: Masaaki Yamada, Princeton University 20-HTIDS20-0017
- **Lower Hybrid Drift Waves and Associated Electron Heating During Guide Field Reconnection** PI: Hantao Ji, Princeton University 20-HTIDS-0-0018
- **Solar Imaging Metasurface Polarimeter (SIMPoL)** PI: Roberto Casini, UCAR 20-HTIDS20-0002
- **Advancement of a Lyot Filter Demonstration Instrument (LFDI) for Space-borne Solar Physics Investigations** PI: Scott Sewell, UCAR 20-HTIDS20-0004
- **Plasma Radiation Combined IN-situ Instrument (PRCINI)** PI: Ian Cohen, JHU/APL 20-HTIDS20-0009 interdisciplinary
- **LIEFSI – Laboratory Investigation of Electric Field Sensor Instabilities** PI: John Bonnell, University of California, Berkeley 20-HTIDS20-0010
- **Compact Ion Mass Spectrometer (CIMS) for Ionospheric Outflow and Cold Magnetospheric Plasma Measurements** PI: Carlos Maldonado, Triad National Security, LLC 20-HTIDS20-0012
- **Solar Neutron TRACKing Instrument (SONTRAC)** PI: Georgia de Nolfo, NASA's GSFC 20-HTIDS20-0014
- **Development of an EMCCD Space Camera for UV Spectroscopy: Probing Nitric Oxide in the Polar Night** PI: Leon Harding, VA Polytec 20-HTIDS20-0015
- **Development of a Novel Nano-Transmitter Plasma Wave Antenna** PI: Bill Amatucci, NRL 20-HTIDS20-0020
- **Multi Look-Direction Magnetic Electron Spectrometer for Auroral Studies** PI: Robert Michell, NASA's GSFC 20-HTIDS20-0021
- **Mass Spectrometry of the Turbopause Region (MSTR)** PI: Chad Fish, Orion Space Solutions 20-HTIDS20-0027
- **CLASS, a Compact Lyman-Alpha Spatial Heterodyne Spectrometer** PI: Seyedeh Sona Hosseini, NASA's JPL 20-HTIDS20-0028
- **Increasing the Dynamic Range of Spaceflight Charged Particle Instruments** PI: Christopher Mouikis, University of New Hampshire, Durham 20-HTIDS20-0031
- **Miniaturized High-Energy-Resolution relativistic electronic Telescope (HERT)-Auburn** PI: Hong Zhao, Auburn University 20-HTIDS20-0034
- **MAGnetometers for Innovation and Capability (MAGIC)** PI: David Miles, University of Iowa SPECIAL PROJECT
- **Plasmasphere Tomography (PlaTo) Mission Study** PI: Wendy Frank, University of Colorado, Boulder 20-HFOS20-0011

2019

- **Laboratory Studies of OH(v) + O Multi-quantum Vibrational Relaxation Required for TIMED/SABER Observations** PI: Konstantinos Kalogerakis, SRI International 19-HTIDS19-0003
- **Fe IX Line Survey and Density Sensitivity Studies in Support of the NASA Heliophysics Program** PI: Daniel Savin, Columbia University 19-HTIDS19-0005
- **Excitation of Whistler-Mode Chorus Waves in a Laboratory Plasma** PI: Xin An, University of California, Los Angeles 19-HTIDS19-0006
- **Investigating Magnetospheric Whistler-Mode Chorus Features Using SPSC Laboratory Experiments** PI: Erik Tejero, NRL 19-HTIDS19-0026
- **Medium Energy Electron Telescope (MEET)** PI: Xinlin Li, University of Colorado 19-HTIDS19-0001
- **MICRO – Magnetograph using Interferometric and Computational imaging for Remote Observations** PI: Neal Hurlburt, Lockheed Martin 19-HTIDS19-0002
- **Fast, Multi-spectral, Polarization-Sensitive IR Detectors for Solar Astronomy from 5 to 100 Microns** PI: Gary Bernstein, University of Notre Dame 19-HTIDS19-0008
- **Technology Development of High Speed CMOS Detectors and Multilayer Mirrors for Dynamic Solar Soft X-Ray Spectral Imaging** PI: Christopher Moore, Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory 19-HTIDS19-0017
- **ACCEPT: A Compact Solar Energetic Particle Telescope** PI: Brian Walsh, Boston University 19-HTIDS19-0019
- **Development and Demonstration of an All Solid-State 4.7 THz Spectrometer Enabling Measurements of Thermospheric Winds, Temperature, and O Density** PI: Sam Yee, Princeton University 19-HTIDS19-0027
- **Development of the Alaska Cubesat Auroral Plasma Spectrometer (ACAPS)** PI: Donald Hampton, Geophysical Institute 19-HTIDS19-0030

2018

- **Laboratory Investigation of Satellite Gas-Surface Interactions for Accurate Construction of Atmospheric Models** PI: Marcin Pillinski, University of Colorado, Boulder 18-HTIDS18-0025
- **Extension of the dE/dx-E Technique Using Silicon Detectors to Below 1 MeV/nucleon** PI: Mark Wiedenbeck, JPL 18-HTIDS18-0008
- **CHIMERA: A Hybrid Search Coil and Fluxgate Magnetometer for Small Spacecraft Missions** PI: David Miles, University of Iowa 18-HTIDS18-0010
- **Small UV Imager for Heliophysics Science Investigations** PI: Thomas Immel, Space Sciences Laboratory/University of California, Berkeley 18-HTIDS18-0060

HELIOSPHERE

Investigations into the origins and behavior of the solar wind, energetic particles, and magnetic fields in the heliosphere, including their interactions with Earth, other planets, and the interstellar medium

MAGNETOSPHERE

Investigations into the physics of the magnetosphere, including the fundamental interactions of plasmas and particles with fields and waves and their coupling to the solar wind and ionosphere

ITM

Investigations into the physics of Earth's ionosphere, thermosphere, and mesosphere, including their coupling to the Earth's lower atmosphere and to the magnetosphere

SOLAR SCIENCE

Investigations into the Sun, including the processes taking place throughout the solar interior and atmosphere, as well as the evolution and cyclic activity of the Sun

H-TIDeS

The technology portfolio is ROSES elements B.8 **Heliophysics Instrument Development for Science** (H-TIDeS) and B.10 **Heliophysics Flight Opportunity Studies** (H-FOS).

H-FOS supports Heliophysics science mission concept studies at the pre-Phase A level.

H-TIDeS includes the **Laboratory Nuclear, Atomic, and Plasma Physics** (LNAPP) and **Instrument Technology Development** (ITD) focus areas. LNAPP supports studies that probe fundamental nuclear, atomic, and plasma physical processes and produce chemical and spectroscopic measurements that support spacecraft observations and atmospheric models. ITD includes innovative instrument and technology development that may be proposed as candidate experiments for future space flight opportunities.

ITD

LNAPP

H-FOS

INTERDISCIPLINARY
Investigations that relate to at least two heliophysics science regimes

66

Active Projects

HESTO

BY THE NUMBERS

2024 STATS

*Only includes projects active in 2024, not those awarded in January 2025.

TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

Visible light recorded during a plasma discharge in TREX at UW-Madison

Modeling Magnetic Reconnection in the Lab to Improve Space Weather Forecasting

Because Earth is embedded in the Sun's extended atmosphere, what happens at the Sun also affects our planet, including its satellites and other technology systems. Earth's magnetic shield helps screens us from the incoming solar wind plasma – most solar particles are deflected around the magnetopause. However, this shielding is not perfect, and through magnetic reconnection, solar particles can penetrate into the near-Earth environment. Magnetic reconnection is a fundamental process in plasmas that converts magnetic energy into particle energy while changing the topology of the magnetic field lines. Since it is the dominant process that couples the solar wind to Earth's magnetosphere, reconnection at the dayside magnetopause and in the magnetotail is of special interest for the Sun-Earth connection and plasma conditions in the near-Earth environment. While reconnection occurs in microscopic diffusion regions, it often governs macroscopic behavior, such as the evolution of solar flares, coronal mass ejections, and magnetic storms in Earth's magnetotail. Although reconnection has been investigated for decades, for experiments to push forward emerging frontiers, new devices that access regimes of fully collisionless plasmas at large spatial scales are necessary. The Terrestrial Reconnection EXperiment (TREX), developed at the University of Wisconsin-Madison, reproduces the celestial phenomenon of magnetic reconnection under controlled and repeatable laboratory conditions. TREX enables researchers to characterize the process in a parameter regime directly relevant to space plasma, with the aim of validating and furthering the theoretical understanding of reconnection.

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Early Career 0 Postdoc 0 Grad 3 Ugrad 2

Alexander Fairchild working in the Electron Beam Ion Trap (EBIT) facility

Unlocking the Sun's Secrets: Laboratory Insights into the Sun's Outer Atmosphere

The Sun's corona, its outermost and hottest atmospheric layer, emits brightly in the extreme ultraviolet (EUV) and X-ray bands. This emission comes from atoms that have been highly ionized by the high temperatures in the corona, forming a plasma of atomic ions and free electrons. By studying this light, scientists learn about the complex and dynamic drivers of solar activity. Many past, current, and future solar observatories focus on measuring EUV spectra from the Fe IX ion, as this ion provides powerful diagnostics for solar physics. Using Fe IX spectra, solar physicists can measure plasma temperature, density, elemental abundances, and flow velocities in the corona. However, atomic data uncertainties concerning spectral line identification and plasma density diagnostics are a major issue in the accurate interpretation of these spectra.

Researchers at Columbia University and Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) have conducted laboratory experiments using the LLNL Electron Beam Ion Trap (EBIT) facility to resolve these uncertainties by unambiguously identifying Fe IX spectral lines and calibrating electron density diagnostics formed by Fe IX line intensity ratios. In particular, the researchers were able to precisely calibrate the electron-density-sensitivity for the intensity ratio of the Fe IX 241.74Å/244.91Å lines, enabling its use as one of the most sensitive density diagnostics for the solar corona.

In addition, the researchers have conducted Fe IX and Fe X line surveys that have provided new line identifications and more precise wavelengths. These data will be useful for current and future Heliophysics missions, providing new measurements that will refine solar models and improve the accuracy of solar observations.

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Early Career 0 Postdoc 1 Grad 0 Ugrad 0

Experimental Observation of the Bifurcated Current Sheet in Two-fluid Magnetic Reconnection Layer

In a prototypical two-dimensional (2D) antiparallel reconnection geometry, the Magnetic Reconnection Experiment (MRX) team has experimentally verified a well-known Petschek-type reconnection layer of double wedge structure and explained by two-fluid dynamics.

In a two-fluid reconnection layer, as electrons and ions move into the reconnection layer with different paths, the magnetized electrons penetrate deep into the reconnection layer, generating a strong potential well in the diffusion region. The shape of the well expands toward the exit of the exhaust region. A kinetic-scale current layer develops at the separatrix region, creating abrupt changes of magnetic field vectors and generating the bifurcated current sheet widely observed in the Heliospheric current sheet. Magnetic field energy is converted to electric field potential energy through the motion of magnetized electrons in the background of non-magnetized ions. While some of the magnetic energy is deposited in the electrons in the electron-diffusion layer, ions gain substantial energy through electrostatic acceleration across the potential well in the broader ion diffusion region. Quantifying this kinetic-scale current sheet layer at the separatrix enabled estimates of the energy partitioning in the two-fluid magnetic reconnection layer.

The MRX team conducted comparisons between laboratory measurements and space observations captured by the Parker Solar Probe (PSP), which showed dominant energy conversion to ions. Numerical simulations to further verify these findings are currently underway.

2D profile of out-of-plane current density measured during two-fluid reconnection shows the current sheet is bifurcated along the separatrix in the downstream region. The potential well and associated ion acceleration are also observed

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Early Career 2 Postdoc 0 Grad 0 Ugrad 0

Novel Magnetic Nano-Transmitter Plasma Wave Antenna

The ability to launch low-frequency plasma waves from space platforms with amplitudes large enough to trigger non-linear wave-particle interactions would enable controlled investigation of key inner radiation belts physics. For example, space observations indicate that in the presence of injected Whistler or Electromagnetic Ion Cyclotron (EMIC) waves with amplitudes exceeding ~0.1 to 1 nT, secondary wave emissions with amplitudes more than tens of dB higher can be triggered, followed by intense nonlinear wave-particle interactions. Conventional space-based electric and magnetic dipole transmitters are too large and too inefficient to inject waves with sufficient amplitudes to investigate this physics.

Under this program, researchers from the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) and the University of Maryland are developing a prototype compact, low-power, single-domain magnetic nanoparticle transmitting antenna (MANTA). MANTA consists of an array of cylindrical, small-diameter, high aspect ratio, multiturn coils, each with an inserted high-permeability (μ) core and phased to produce optimum coupling to the selected Whistler or EMIC mode. MANTA prototype antennas arranged in phase controlled crossed-dipole configurations, currently being tested in the NRL Space Physics Simulation Chamber (SPSC), have confirmed the large gains in transmitted plasma wave amplitude. The experiments confirm a key prediction that high- μ cores increase MANTA radiation resistance.

The ability to drive large amplitude EMIC waves presents the opportunity to exploit nonlinear plasma processes leading to Triggered EMIC (TEMIC) emissions that leverage the energy of the trapped energetic particle populations to provide another ~30 dB amplification of the injected waves, resulting in scattering of trapped radiation belt particles. A prototype for future testing on the International Space Station is currently under development.

Prototype MANTA being tested in scaled space plasma conditions in NRL's SPSC

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Early Career 1 Postdoc 0 Grad 1 Ugrad 0

TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

TECNAs with dipole (top) and log-spiral antennas (bottom) for linear and circular polarization detection in the long-wave infrared regime

Multi-Spectral, Multi-Polarization, Long-Wave, IR Detectors for Space Weather Analysis

Coronal mass ejections (CMEs) can affect space weather and cause harm to satellites and the power grid on Earth. Information contained in mid- and long-wavelength infrared (IR) radiation, along with its polarization, could help us understand and predict CMEs, but is difficult and expensive to obtain. CMEs are caused by strong magnetic fields, which are capable of polarizing light. As a result, they can be studied by analyzing the Stokes parameters of IR light that travels through magnetic regions. Our novel IR sensors do this across multiple wavelengths simultaneously, thus improving simulations and increasing our understanding of the mechanisms of solar flares and CMEs.

The team at Notre Dame is developing thermoelectrically coupled nanoantennas (TECNAs) based on the same basic principle as satellite dishes but a million times smaller, which is made possible by nanofabrication methods. A nanoantenna is suspended above a cavity that thermally insulates the antenna and condenses the light to increase sensitivity. The IR light heats the antenna, which heats a nanothermocouple with a voltage proportional to the light intensity.

The geometry of the antenna determines the resonant wavelength and polarization selectivity. The length of linear dipole antennas provides relatively narrow-band operation with dominant linear polarization selectivity. Spiral antennas are relatively broadband and are primarily selective to circular polarization. The direction of the spiral dictates the handedness of sensitivity to circular polarization. Combining dipole and spiral antennas of various sizes in a focal plane array enables us to simultaneously determine the Stokes parameters at different wavelengths, providing a more cost-effective way to gain critical information about CMEs.

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19-HTIDS19-0008

Early Career	Postdoc	Grad	Ugrad
2	1	1	10

MICRO - All the Sun, All the Time: Minuscule Magnetographs for Space Weather

The Sun's magnetic field, generated by the solar dynamo, is the cause of all major space weather in our solar system: from the 22-year magnetic cycle that modulates the total solar irradiance, to global coronal magnetic fields that structure the solar wind, to magnetic eruptions from active regions that power coronal mass ejections and trigger major geomagnetic storms. Yet we have only consistently measured the solar magnetic field from one vantage point near Earth, missing approximately 3/4 of the activity at any one time. Simultaneous solar measurements from multiple vantage points are essential for fully understanding space weather.

MICRO, the Magnetograph using Interferometric and Computational imaging for Remote Observations, is a disruptive imaging technology to enable these measurements. It collapses the optical elements of a solar magnetograph into a single, multilayer, photonic wafer, thus reducing the size and weight by orders of magnitude. Instead of painstaking manual assembly of traditional designs, these wafers are printed using photolithographic methods – leading to a dramatic reduction in integration cost with improved reproducibility. Together these revolutionary properties expand hosting opportunities and enable the formation of novel constellations combining traditional and non-traditional platforms for monitoring solar oscillations and magnetic fields.

Ultra-compact, wafer-like photonic imagers could be carried on any spacecraft as a prime instrument or embedded with solar arrays

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Early Career	Postdoc	Grad	Ugrad
1	0	1	0

Stanford UCDAVIS LOCKHEED MARTIN

Probing Nitric Oxide from Low Earth Orbit with an EMCCD Ultraviolet Space Camera

Heliophysics has long benefited from ultraviolet (UV) and optical remote sensing of the Sun, planets, and Earth's upper atmosphere. Observations of aurora, airglow, and nightglow have been crucial in revealing the processes controlling solar particle acceleration through Earth's atmosphere. Our understanding of the Sun and planetary response to solar activity have been largely driven by remote sensing inaccessible to smaller spacecraft. We are now in an exciting period where space-based remote sensing has transformed from reliance on large spacecraft to exponentially-increasing opportunities on small satellites.

Building on the successes of Virginia Tech (VT) sounding rocket programs, we have accelerated development of new space technologies with the goal of space qualifying a UV camera to probe the coupling of the middle and upper atmosphere by space weather. Our mission uses a novel stellar occultation technique in low Earth orbit to determine the nitric oxide altitude profile during polar winter, which is closely linked to the destruction of ozone – a vital ingredient for life on Earth.

Teams at VT's National Security Institute (NSI) and Space@VT have coupled the power of the Electron Multiplying CCD (EMCCD), a sensor capable of unprecedented levels of spectral sensitivity, with a specialized approach to UV instrumentation in a cubesat, thus paving the way for the most thorough investigation of this phenomenon to date. Crucially, EMCCDs have been selected for future NASA flagship missions, including the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope. Merging the sensor and optical imaging technologies developed through this program is extremely relevant to the next decade of space imaging and a strong candidate for upcoming NASA flight opportunities.

Custom space telescope coupled to a VT cryogenic dewar housing the delta-doped EMCCD flight sensor and electronics

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Early Career	Postdoc	Grad	Ugrad
2	0	3	7

Developing Spaceflight-Qualified Tools for Imaging Spectro-Polarimetry

This project advances the spaceborne readiness of a temperature-compensated, wavelength tunable birefringent (Lyot) optical filter. Tunable Lyot filters have a long history of enabling measurements of the solar photosphere, chromosphere, and corona through their inherently large etendue, rapid tunability, narrow bandpass, and wavelength versatility. They are typically inserted within a telescope's optical system and enable high-resolution spectral imaging of the Sun. The HAO team is advancing and ruggedizing this technology in two parallel activities. The first is by developing a space-qualified tuning control board to stably adjust a filter's transmission spectrum to an arbitrary wavelength position, irrespective of changes in the filter's environmental temperature. The power consumption for the tuning control board is <1 Watt. In the second, the team is developing opto-mechanical bonding techniques to enable the filter to survive the vibrational loads of launch vehicles, as well as eliminate the outgassing risk of optical coupling gels and fluids used in terrestrial filters.

The Lyot Filter Demonstration Instrument (LFDI) filter is specifically designed for a small (6-12U) mission, although larger filters can be made with the same approach, limited only by the available sizes of optical-quality birefringent materials. Naturally-occurring minerals like calcite (CaCO3) limit realizable clear apertures to ~30 mm, while laboratory grown crystals like lithium niobate (LiNbO3) will enable filters of over 100 mm. The HAO team's demonstration instrument is designed to sample the core and wings of the H-Alpha solar emission line at 656.28 nm, but the technology is immediately extensible to all visible and near-infrared wavelengths and is well suited for inclusion within scientific telescope payloads.

LFDI H-Alpha filter and tuning control board

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Early Career	Postdoc	Grad	Ugrad
2	0	0	1

TECHNOLOGY HIGHLIGHTS

World's Smallest Schottky Diode Enables Measurement of Thermionic Winds

TeraHz Limb Sounder (TLS) is a low-mass, low-power, high spectral resolution heterodyne spectro-polarimeter operating in the TeraHz (THz) frequency regime designed to remotely measure thermospheric wind, temperature, and atomic oxygen density profiles from a low-Earth orbit platform. TLS resolves the Doppler line shapes of atomic oxygen emissions at 2.06 THz (145 μm) and 4.7 THz (63 μm) and uses their polarimetric properties to improve its measurement precisions.

The TLS team at Johns Hopkins University's Advanced Physics Laboratory (APL) and NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) are building very low parasitic THz diodes that have sensitivity at 4.7 THz to detect the neutral oxygen line in the 100-400 km altitude. TLS can, for the first time, measure neutral wind profiles globally, both day and night, in an altitude region

where most of the ion-neutral energy/momentum coupling takes place and the neutral atmosphere responds to external energy inputs. These measurements provide critical observational constraints to the complex dynamics in the coupled lower atmosphere/thermosphere/ionosphere/magnetosphere system, as highlighted in the 2012 Heliophysics Decadal Survey and 2014 Heliophysics Science and Technology Roadmap for 2014-2033. The TLS instrument supports the science objectives of Dynamical Atmosphere Ionosphere Coupling (DYNAMIC), a 2014 Roadmap-recommended Solar Terrestrial Probes (STP) mission, which directly benefits future Heliophysics mission planning and implementation. In addition, TLS is compact, small, light-weight, low power, and ideal to supporting future cost-effective science missions in implementing the 2012 Decadal Survey's Diversify, Realize, Integrate, Venture, Educate (DRIVE) initiative.

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APES in Space: A New Approach to Ionospheric Observation

The Active Plasma and E-field Sounders (APES) mission concept targets height-resolved observation of the ionospheric plasma surrounding Earth using a novel technique: swept-frequency radio transmissions passing between satellites to 'sound out' the ionosphere. This approach stems from the Alouette mission launched in 1962, which performed sounding from a single spacecraft. If successful, the new cooperative approach could be applied to a satellite constellation to provide ubiquitous observational coverage of the space environment.

APES aims to resolve orders-of-magnitude errors found in models of transionospheric radio propagation near the midlatitude trough. This region is formed when powerful electric fields originating at higher altitudes (close to the 'plasmopause') hollow out the plasma, generating irregularities near the trough walls. The trough also hosts the 'Steve' optical phenomenon, which was recently brought to light by amateur auroral photographers. APES supports in situ instruments that will indicate which physical mechanism(s) are responsible for generating plasma irregularities in the trough.

APES consists of two cubesats that use propulsion to achieve an elliptical 350x800 km orbit in $>50^\circ$ inclination. Named in honor of two of the first primates in space, APES-Enos has two 6-m booms, while APES-Ham has six 2.5-m booms. Enos hosts a radio transmitter for ionospheric sounding, plus in situ neutral and plasma probes. Ham hosts a radio receiver, plus in situ vector electric field and plasma probes. The electric field instrument shares the same booms as the radio receiver. APES will overfly ground-based radio transmitters (e.g., Super Dual Auroral Radar Network radars, HF timing transmitters, ionosondes) to characterize transionospheric propagation.

APES' two spacecraft will 'sound out' ionospheric electron density profiles along the orbital track

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Unraveling Electron Acceleration in the Radiation Belt via High-energy Resolution Measurements

Earth's radiation belts are filled with relativistic electrons in the MeV energy range and above. These highly-energetic electrons pose significant threats to avionics and humans in space, making understanding their dynamics an urgent need. As CubeSats increasingly play a more prominent role, enabling missions at a far lower cost, they become ideal vehicles for conducting such scientific investigations.

The miniaturized High-Energy-Resolution relativistic electron Telescope (HERT) is a compact telescope designed for a 6U CubeSat mission in a geosynchronous transfer orbit (GTO). HERT aims to provide high-energy resolution ($dE/E < 12\%$) measurements of 1 to 7 MeV electrons at

GTO. These measurements will enable a novel method to differentiate the two main acceleration mechanisms – inward radial transport and local acceleration – and solve the longstanding question of how electrons in Earth's radiation belts are accelerated to relativistic energies.

Building on heritage from the Van Allen Probes' Relativistic Electron Proton Telescope (REPT) and REPTile-2 on CubeSat Inner Radiation Belt Experiment (CIRBE), HERT comprises a stack of nine solid-state silicon detectors in a telescope configuration, a beryllium window to block lower energy electrons, and a tantalum collimator to enforce the required field of view (33°). HERT's responses investigated using Geant4 simulations project a nominal energy resolution of $\sim 5\%$ for 1.5 to 3 MeV electrons and greater than $\sim 12\%$ for other core energy channels. Results of radiation testing conducted with a Cobalt-60 source suggest HERT electronics can sustain a total ionizing dose of ~ 65 krad, meeting instrument performance requirements in GTO.

With its high energy resolution and miniaturized design, HERT will greatly advance the quantitative understanding of relativistic electron acceleration in Earth's radiation belts.

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Early Career 4 Postdoc 0 Grad 3 Ugrad 1

Studying Plasmasphere Dynamics Using a Constellation of Spacecraft

Plasmasphere Tomography (PlaTo) is a mission concept designed to address several outstanding questions about the plasmasphere. The plasmasphere is a cold (~ 1 eV) and dense (~ 100 – $10,000$ cm^{-3}) plasma population of ionospheric origin that extends from ~ 1000 km to $\sim 32,000$ km altitude. This dense region of plasma is important to understanding the dynamics of the magnetosphere and wave-particle interactions. While many aspects of plasmasphere dynamics have been known for some time, many details and aspects of these are still unknown. Specifically, PlaTo will determine what causes the structuring of the density, the instabilities contributing to structuring, and how the rate of refilling changes over the course of the refilling process.

The PlaTo mission is a constellation of sixteen spacecraft spread across two orbits around the Earth – six in an orbit with lower apogee and ten in an orbit with higher apogee. Each spacecraft transmits a pair of phased radio signals to the rest of the constellation. Changes in the radio signal (phase shift and group delay) are used to determine the total electron content (TEC) between each pair of spacecraft. Like a medical CAT scan, these measurements are inverted into two-dimensional images, or maps, of the plasmasphere density, exposing the dynamics of this plasma population.

The number of spacecraft, the radio frequencies they use, and the transmission power used to make the measurements to sufficient accuracy and spatial/temporal resolution to address these questions are enabling keys for the PlaTo investigation.

Each PlaTo spacecraft transmits a pair of phased radio signals to the rest of the constellation

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COLLABORATION WITH NASA STMD

The NASA **Space Technology Mission Directorate (STMD) Small Business Innovation Research/Small Business Technology Transfer (SBIR/STTR)** program is part of America's Seed Fund, the nation's largest source of early-stage funding for innovative technologies. Through this program, entrepreneurs, startups, and small businesses can receive funding and non-monetary support to build, mature, and commercialize technologies, advancing NASA missions and helping to solve important problems facing our country.

In June 2024, NASA selected nearly 250 small business teams to develop new technologies that address agency priorities. About 34% of the selected companies were first-time recipients. Each team receives \$150k to establish the merit and feasibility of their innovation, with a total NASA investment of \$44.85M. Featured are some newly-selected projects relevant to Heliophysics.

An Advanced Surface Flux Transport Model for Space Weather

Jon Linker (linkerj@predsci.com), Predictive Science Inc

Develop an Open Source Flux Transport model to acquire and assimilate solar magnetograms and rapidly produce multiple realizations at high resolution. It will estimate the present state of the Sun's surface magnetic field, allowing space weather models to produce more accurate predictions.

Containerized Models to Predict Ionospheric Scintillations

Jeffrey Marino (jmarino@ensembleconsultancy.com), Ensemble Government Services, LLC

Develop a pipeline targeting ionospheric scintillation characterization, monitoring, and prediction specifically to deliver precise scintillation indices estimates for amplitude and phase through the use of Machine Learning.

Applications for Differentiating Cybersecurity and Space Environment Hazards to Satellites

Janet Green (jgreen@spacehaz.com), Space Hazards Applications, LLC

Provide a toolset to give commercial and government satellite operators real-time and retrospective awareness of space weather hazards from both man-made (cybersecurity) threats and natural hazards from the space plasma and radiation environment.

Commercial Data Assimilation Tool for Operational Thermospheric Density

Shaylah Mutschler (smutschler@spacewx.com), Space Environment Technologies

Provide a commercial data assimilation tool combining various data sources to provide a corrected thermospheric nowcast global density state. Such a "nowcast" can be combined with Space Environment Technologies' operational forecast space weather indices to produce forecasts 2-3 days in the future.

Enhanced System-Level Single Event Effects for Space Weather Operations

Zachary Robinson (zachary@5thgait.com), Fifth Gait Technologies, Inc

Enhance the Space Ionizing Radiation Environment and Effects (SIRE2) family of tools to improve its ability to calculate the expected upset rate inside a simulated electronic board or package at the system-level for space weather operations.

Production of Magnetic Core Materials for Flux-Gate Magnetometers

Edward Salley (esalley@skyvisionsciences.com), SkyVision Sciences, LLC

Develop a process for fabricating Mo-Permalloy, which is a material used as the core material in advanced magnetometers and is becoming increasingly difficult to source.

THz LO Sources for Heliophysics

Theodore Reck (reck@vadiodes.com), Virginia Diodes, Inc

Develop a new local oscillator source in the 1 to 5THz frequency range, which can be used in the measurement of wind and temperature in the lower thermosphere and E-region ionosphere using terahertz limb sounding measurements of the OI thermal emissions at 2.06 or 4.75 THz.

Quasistatic Release Mechanism

Oliver Fildes (ofildes@helio.space), Heliospace Corporation

Develop a resettable release mechanism that exports near-zero shock during actuation and can be utilized for deploying observatory systems and subsystems. The mechanism is designed to be field resettable and scalable from cubesats to flagship missions.

Solar Update Neural Network for Improved Event Prediction

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Develop a Solar Update Neural Network for Improved Event (SUNNIE) prediction using a Physics-Informed Neural Network (PINN) architecture. It will enhance existing models for Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) event forecasting by integrating underlying numerical solvers directly into the training cycle.

A key HESTO objective is to expand collaboration with NASA STMD to accelerate development of critical technologies that will drive Heliophysics research over the next decade and beyond. By leveraging STMD's innovative programs, HESTO is enhancing the technological foundation needed to advance our scientific understanding of the Sun and its interactions with the solar system.

One ongoing HESTO and STMD collaboration is the Small Business Innovation Research (SBIR) program, which fosters development of innovative space technologies. SBIR-supported projects have not only advanced Heliophysics capabilities but also have contributed to the growth of commercial space technology solutions.

To further mature and validate technologies in relevant environments, HESTO is working with STMD to utilize the Flight Opportunities Program. This partnership provides access to commercial flight providers offering payload integration and flight services for technology demonstrations in suborbital, high-altitude, reduced-gravity, and orbital environments. These flight opportunities—ranging from suborbital rocket-powered vehicles to high-altitude balloons and hosted orbital platforms—enable critical technology maturation in alignment with 2024 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics priorities.

A notable example of HESTO/STMD collaboration is the Advanced Composite Solar Sail System (ACS3). ACS3 is a sub-scale Small Spacecraft Technology program flight demonstration in low Earth orbit aimed at validating the performance of deployable composite booms for solar sail propulsion on future missions. ACS3 will pave the way for larger, more advanced solar sail missions. In addition to demonstrating key sail deployment and performance metrics, HESTO and STMD are collaborating to assess long-term sail durability, maneuvering capabilities, and acceleration characteristics. The 2024 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics reinforces the importance of advancing solar sail technology to enable missions that significantly improve space weather forecasting lead times.

Through these partnerships, HESTO and STMD are driving innovation in Heliophysics technologies, ensuring future missions have the tools needed to explore and understand the Sun's dynamic influence on the solar system.

Sensors and Instruments (TX08)

Remote Sensing Instruments and Sensors (TX08.1)

Detectors and Focal Planes (TX08.1.1)

In Situ Instruments and Sensors (TX08.3)

Field and Particle Sensors (TX08.3.1)

- HELIOSPHERE
- MAGNETOSPHERE
- SOLAR SCIENCE
- ITM
- INTERDISCIPLINARY

INFUSION HIGHLIGHTS

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Rocket Mission to Quantify Nightglow Mechanism Discovered in Laboratory Experiments

The hydroxyl radical Meinel band emission, named after astronomer Aden B. Meinel who first observed it in 1948, is a prominent feature in the visible and near-infrared region of the Earth's nightglow spectrum. This emission is an important target for remote sensing of the mesosphere and lower thermosphere atmospheric regions. Detailed knowledge of the underlying mechanisms for production and loss of vibrationally-excited hydroxyl, OH(v), is critical input for the analysis and interpretation of atmospheric observations. Despite significant progress over the past few decades, several gaps persist in our understanding of the processes responsible for the OH(v) Meinel band emission.

Laser-based laboratory studies at SRI International supported by HESTO's LNAPP program provided experimental evidence that multi-quantum vibrational relaxation in OH(v) + O collisions can lead to production of electronically excited O(1D) atoms. An important implication for Earth's nightglow is that OH(v) + O collisions represent a previously unrecognized source of the O2 atmospheric band emission [doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aau9255].

In 2020, a collaborative sounding rocket mission was successfully proposed to the Swedish Space Agency with the science objective to investigate this recently discovered nightglow source and quantify its influence on mesospheric nightglow emissions. The mission, Oxygen and its Role In Generating and Influencing Nightglow (ORIGIN), is led by the Meteorology Department of Stockholm University, Sweden. The payload photometer module, Hydroxyl Oxygen Profile Explorer (HOPE), has flight heritage from the Oxygen Species and Thermospheric Airglow in The Earth's Sky (O-STATES) rocket campaign. The ORIGIN mission's two rocket launches of the same payload within a couple of weeks will take place at the Esrange Space Center, Sweden, in early 2025.

Launching 2025

HOPE photometer module with ion, electron, Faraday, and O-atom sensors

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Dynamic Soft X-ray CMOS Detectors Catch 'Flashy' Solar Flares

The Swift Solar Activity X-ray Imager-Rocket (SSAXI-Rocket) team has developed the next generation of soft X-ray and ultraviolet (UV) high-speed readout detector and camera systems. These systems, designed for future satellite missions to observe the Sun and astrophysical objects, use complementary metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) sensor detectors. The detectors readout images faster (>10 Hz) than instruments currently available on existing observatories and are capable of uncovering the solar flare plasma features that remain obscured to current detector technologies.

The SSAXI-Rocket sensors, designed in partnership between the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics (CfA), SRI International, and NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL), are intended to make observations of the soft X-ray peak emission phase of a C-class or greater solar flare. The technology has peak sensitivity to 10 MK solar plasma, similar to current High Resolution Coronal Imager Flare (HiC-Flare) instruments, and provides opportunities for exploration of additional parameter space, including the variability in heating and energy transport of solar flares. The team's SSAXI-Rocket instrument combines X-ray focusing optics and a high-speed readout detector to image solar flare soft X-rays at a high time cadence without image saturation and pixel signal blooming into the adjacent pixels. This enables an unprecedented opportunity to image large solar flares' hot plasma unobscured, with high contrast imaging.

The SSAXI-Rocket instrument was funded through NASA's Low Cost Access to Space program to ride on the NASA HiC-Flare rocket as part of its ongoing Flare Campaign. The next iterations of the SSAXI-Rocket CMOS sensors and cameras are planned for implementation on future sounding rocket, cubesat, and large satellite missions.

SSAXI-Rocket CMOS detector camera system during X-ray testing in a vacuum chamber

Launched 2024

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CubeWind: Measuring Atmospheric Density, Winds, and Temperature in Space

Winds constitute a key element of the behavior of atmospheres, including in Earth's thermosphere. Understanding how the thermosphere interacts with various aspects of the Sun-Earth system, including the magnetosphere/ionosphere, incident solar energy, geomagnetic activity, gravity waves generated in the troposphere, and anthropogenic influences, requires knowledge of several thermospheric quantities over a range of distance and temporal scales. One of the most important of these aspects is winds, as they are both indicators and agents of variability and evolution within the Sun-Earth system. However, thermospheric winds measurements have been historically difficult – especially the in situ winds measurements that are the “gold standard” – impeding our understanding of the thermosphere. The CubeWind project aims to improve this by enabling in situ, low-resource measurements of thermospheric winds on missions as small as cubesats.

The CubeWind team is miniaturizing existing winds measurement instrumentation so low-resource missions, like cubesats, can include these instruments in their payloads. Current winds packages can require payload resources as high as 10 kg, 40,000 cm³, and 25 W, which is clearly not compatible with cubesat capabilities. The CubeWind team's miniaturization goal is to fit a 6U cubesat. The team has performed trade studies on the best route to miniaturization, developed and lab-tested a one-axis breadboard sensor, designed a two-axis sensor scheduled for fabrication, and has developed a concept for the in-track component of winds. The team plans to have a pair of test sensors ready to fly on the Dynamos, Winds, and Electric Fields in the Daytime Lower Ionosphere 3 (Dynamo-3) sounding rocket in June 2026.

Prototype CubeWind sensor in molecular beam test facility

Launching 2026

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New Technology to Increase the Dynamic Range of an Ion Plasma Detector

Electrostatic analyzers (ESA) are crucial instruments in space plasma physics, enabling measurement of the charged particle distributions that are key to understanding important processes, such as solar wind-magnetosphere interactions and dynamics of planetary ionospheres. Accurate measurements of plasma properties, such as particle energy and density, are essential for understanding these phenomena. Covering the dynamic range of the flux over the full range of conditions for even one of these plasma populations is a challenge. The difficulty is increased if measuring more than one population with the same instrument, or even if measuring the same population at vastly different heliocentric distances. Standard ESA designs struggle to measure high- and low-particle fluxes within a single instrument configuration, often requiring multiple entrance systems or analyzers to meet the science objectives of a space mission, increasing complexity, mass, and power requirements.

The team at the University of New Hampshire has developed a modification to a standard top-cap analyzer that increases the measured dynamic range for ions entering an instrument by up to three orders of magnitude. The addition of a secondary electrode within the ESA channel that can be controlled separately in an automated manner allows for dynamic adjustment of the instrument's response to the fast-changing plasma environment.

This new design will be used in two Solar Wind Plasma Sensor (SWiPS) instruments on the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Space weather Observations at L1 – 2 (SOL-2) and SOL-3 observatories at Lagrange point 1 (L1) for monitoring the upstream solar wind. Because of this new design, for the first time, solar wind measurements will cover the full range of solar wind parameters for more than 99% of conditions.

Prototype ESA with dynamic geometric factor control

Launching 2025 & 2032

INFUSION HIGHLIGHTS

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Ionospheric Plasma and Contamination Monitoring on the International Space Station

Space weather forecasting is inhibited by a lack of measurements of constituent ion populations, which have two sources near Earth: the solar wind and the polar wind. The solar wind (predominantly hydrogen, alpha particles, and high charge-state heavy ions) emanates steadily from the Sun. The polar wind, composed of singly ionized atoms and molecules (atomic hydrogen (H+), atomic helium (He+), and atomic oxygen (O+), plus atomic nitrogen (N+), molecular nitrogen (N2+), molecular oxygen (O2+), and nitrogen oxide (NO+)), emanates from Earth's ionosphere. Ionospheric outflow, the process by which low-energy ions leave Earth's atmosphere and enter near-Earth space, is an area of significant study. However, typical mass spectrometers cannot distinguish between N+ and O+ ions due to their similar masses. This ambiguity is problematic, as these ions' behavior in space differs due to their upper atmospheric sources (different scale heights and photoionization), transport (different behaviors in electric and magnetic fields), and loss mechanisms (e.g., neutralization via charge exchange with ambient neutral H or geocoronal H0). Poor knowledge about the differences in source, transport, and loss of N+ and O+ makes it impossible to validate space weather models and hinders space weather prediction capabilities.

Autonomous Ion Mass Spectrometer Sentry (AIMSS) is designed to make high mass resolution observations of the ionospheric plasma and measure contamination caused by ionospheric plasma interaction with thruster plumes from spacecraft visiting the International Space Station (ISS). Such thruster particles degrade optical and thermal surfaces and increase surface charging.

AIMSS, currently being built and tested at Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), will fly on the Space Test Program – Houston 11 (STP-H11) mission to the ISS in 2026. This will provide on-orbit data to validate AIMSS performance and inform future improvements in instruments destined for the magnetosphere.

Electro-optic simulation of the AIMSS sensor head discriminating ion species with incident energy of 534 eV

Launching 2026

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Revealing the Trajectories and Energy Distributions of Solar Flares

During a solar flare, magnetic energy is rapidly and violently released. Much of this energy accelerates charged particles to relativistic speeds, while heating the solar atmosphere to 50 MK. The energy conversion mechanisms and particle propagation of these processes are not well understood due to limitations in existing instrumentation. In particular, the electron angular distribution, a prime diagnostic tool of the acceleration mechanism and transport, is poorly known.

Solar Polarization and Directivity X-Ray Experiment (PADRE) is a 12U cubesat observatory with two instruments, Solar HARd x-ray Polarimeter (SHARP) and Measuring Directivity to Determine Electron Anisotropy (MeDDEA), designed to observe the Sun in the hard X-ray bands from low Earth orbit. Both instruments investigate accelerated electron angular distribution, with SHARP made possible through past H-TIDeS program developments.

The Space Sciences Laboratory (SSL) team has been developing solar X-ray detectors based on Timepix3, a read-out chip developed by the European Council for Nuclear Research (CERN). Coupled with Cadmium Telluride crystals, it can detect individual hard X-ray photons with high contrast and high spatial resolution (small pixels). In SHARP, arrays of these detectors surround a Beryllium cylinder. Incoming X-rays that may be polarized scatter off of the cylinder and are detected by the Timepix3 detectors. Comparing the amount of X-rays in each detector determines the X-ray polarization which, in turn, determines the angular distribution of flare-accelerated electrons, a quantity that, other than a handful of ambiguous cases, is currently unknown.

PADRE measurements are vital to constraining flare particle acceleration scenarios and answering the NASA Heliophysics Research Program's goal to "Discover and characterize fundamental processes that occur both within the heliosphere and throughout the universe."

PADRE is currently undergoing flight testing at UCB's SSL

Launching 2025

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Broad-band Reflective Multilayer Coatings for High-Resolution EUV Spectroscopy

The goal of this research project is to develop reflective optical coatings that operate near normal incidence over a broad spectral band in the extreme ultraviolet (EUV) portion of the electro-magnetic spectrum. These multilayer coatings can then be deposited onto focusing mirrors and reflective diffraction gratings to construct high-resolution spectroscopic instruments for investigating the physics of the solar atmosphere. These new coatings will enable the next generation of satellite instruments for solar EUV spectroscopy, just as narrow-band ("periodic") multilayers developed in past decades enabled satellite instruments for solar EUV imaging, including the Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA) instrument on NASA's Solar Dynamics Observatory.

Periodic EUV multilayer coatings, like those used on AIA, typically comprise a stack of many identical, nanometer-scale bi-layers of optically dissimilar materials arranged to provide constructive interference over a narrow band of EUV wavelengths. In contrast, these new broad-band multilayer coatings are non-periodic (the thickness of each layer in the stack is different), to reflect a wide range of EUV wavelengths. While periodic coatings can be designed analytically, non-periodic coatings are designed numerically, using a genetic optimization algorithm. The team has developed and tested a number of new non-periodic coating designs involving several different multilayer material combinations. Normal incidence reflectance measurements made using synchrotron radiation demonstrate these coatings can achieve excellent performance over the 17 to 50 nm wavelength range.

The Sun Coronal Ejection Tracker (SunCET) mission, targeted for launch in 2025, will utilize one of the new broad-band coatings developed through this research. Other instruments using these new broad-band multilayer coatings are also being proposed for solar physics and stellar astrophysics applications.

Launching 2025

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Making Ultra-fast Electron Measurements in Multiple Directions in the Aurora

The energetic electrons that drive the aurora have a rich, dynamic structure that still is not fully understood. Much of what we know about these electrons comes from instruments with fundamental limitations in their ability to sample multiple energies with high time resolution. To overcome these limitations, a team at NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC) is using an innovative approach to enhance measurement capabilities by more than an order of magnitude—revealing new information about the amazing physics at play within the aurora.

Typical electron instruments rely on electrostatic deflection, which requires changing voltages to select different electrons energies to measure. These instruments have provided almost all of the in situ electron measurements made inside the aurora. They are excellent for observing on a timescale of 1.0 to 0.1 sec, but they fundamentally cannot observe to millisecond timescales due to the time it takes to sweep through multiple voltages.

The Acute Precipitating Electron Spectrometer-360 (APES-360) is a multi look-direction magnetic electron spectrometer for auroral studies that enables measurement of electrons in more than one direction. The team employed operating principles from previous instruments updated to accommodate a multi-look direction geometry that covers a 360-degree field of view using 16 different sectors. This required overcoming several technical challenges; in particular, the electronics design had to accommodate many more anodes and its associated circuitry in a small form factor. Although APES-360 was designed to fit a cubesat form factor to enable studies of the aurora, the instrument could also ultimately be flown on larger orbital missions.

In February 2025, two APES-360 prototypes flew into the aurora on the Ground Imaging to Rocket investigation of Auroral Fast Features (GIRAFF) sounding rocket mission from Poker Flat Research Range, Alaska.

APES-360 multi look-direction magnetic electron spectrometer

Launched 2025

INFUSION HIGHLIGHTS

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17-HTIDS17-0002

Solar Gamma-Ray Imaging and Polarimetry Infused into Astrophysics

The Gamma-Ray Imager/Polarimeter for Solar flares (GRIPS) instrument provides a near-optimal combination of high-resolution imaging, spectroscopy, and polarimetry of solar-flare gamma-ray/hard X-ray emissions from ~20 keV to >~10 MeV. Attaining high-resolution imaging and spectroscopy in this energy range during solar flares is key to understanding poorly-understood energy release and particle acceleration processes.

The GRIPS team, led by University of California, Berkeley's Space Sciences Laboratory (UCB/SSL) and in partnership with NASA, has been developing new three-dimensional (3D) position sensitive germanium detectors (GeD) able to resolve the energy, polarization, and location (down to 0.5 mm) of individual photon interactions within a crystal. The individual detectors are 7.5 x 7.5 x 1.5 cm with a typical energy resolution of 3.5 at 59.5 keV. The team has also developed custom Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) electronics to read out these detectors.

The team has test flown this new instrument technology on the GRIPS and COSI balloon missions. The technology is also being leveraged by Compton Spectrometer and Imager (COSI), a NASA Small Explorer (SMEX) astrophysics mission. The COSI SMEX mission is a wide-field gamma-ray telescope (0.2 to 5 MeV) that will study energetic phenomena in the Milky Way and beyond, including the creation and destruction of matter and antimatter and the energetic deaths of stars.

GRIPS 3D GeD with 54 cm² active area

Launching 2027

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17-HTIDS17-0010

A Flexible Commercial Magneto-Inductive Magnetometer for Heliophysics

A joint team from the University of Michigan (UM) Magnetometer Laboratory and the Space Physics Research Laboratory (SPRL) have developed a new instrument based on a novel commercial magnetometer, the Positioning Navigation Intelligence (PNI) Sensor Corporation's magneto-inductive magnetometer. Unlike traditional spaceflight magnetometers, this new sensor does not use an analog-to-digital converter, making it more tolerant to radiation than typical fluxgate magnetometers. The small commercial PNI magnetometers, each about the size of a US quarter, combined with custom readout electronics, form a compact instrument able to reach research-quality sensitivity. The PNI sensor uses <10 milliwatts of power and weighs about 5 grams. Its compact size will allow it to be flown easily by many types of spacecraft or placed onto multiple locations on a single spacecraft.

In combination with a traditional fluxgate magnetometer built by NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center, the PNI sensor is part of the Noise Eliminating Magnetometer Instrument in a Small Integrated System (NEMISIS) dual-sensor instrument that will fly on two upcoming missions. The Heliophysics Environmental and Radiation Measurement Experiment Suite (HERMES) mission is a space weather payload designed to study Earth's magnetotail and the solar wind from the Gateway Habitat And Logistics Outpost (HALO) module's unique polar lunar orbit. HERMES will establish the capabilities of an on-board space-weather payload to support deep-space and long-term human exploration. NEMISIS is also part of the next Heliophysics flagship mission, the Geospace Dynamics Constellation (GDC). GDC will study the processes that govern the dynamics of Earth's upper atmospheric envelope, the outermost layer that shields and protects our planet.

Launching 2025 & TBD

One of the compact (~50 g, 55x36 mm) UM/SPRL sensors designed for NASA HERMES/NEMISIS

HESTO PATHFINDER

Pathfinder: Bridging the Gap from Concept to Flight

HESTO Pathfinder plays a critical role in advancing Heliophysics technologies across the gap from early-stage development to flight readiness. It provides a structured pathway for promising instruments and technologies to progress beyond the proof-of-concept stage toward integration into larger Heliophysics science missions.

Pathfinder focuses on **maturing technologies** for potential infusion into larger missions, such as Explorers-class missions. By promoting technology flight demonstration through **rideshare access**, Pathfinder leverages cost-effective validation of highly promising technologies in relevant operational environments. This initiative builds upon advancements made through NASA's Heliophysics Technology and Instrument Development for Science (H-TIDeS) program.

Currently, Pathfinder funding is awarded to Principal Investigators (PIs) who secure their own rideshare opportunities, focusing Pathfinder funds on technology maturation rather than flight costs. This approach is cost effective while maximizing the potential for successful technology infusion into future Heliophysics missions. We look forward to making continued investments in new Pathfinder projects and our PIs.

Space Weather Iowa Instrument (SWIM): The First Pathfinder-Funded Project

In 2024, HESTO Pathfinder reached a significant milestone by funding its first project: Space Weather Iowa Instrument (SWIM). SWIM is a magnetometer radiometer instrument that integrates four innovative technologies, two of which were developed through previous HESTO-funded projects.

1. **MAGnetometers for Innovation and Capability (MAGIC)** – This technology demonstration incorporates newly developed ferromagnetic materials into a compact fluxgate sensor, adapting the Tesseract sensor design.
2. **Chimera Hybrid Magnetometer** – Utilizing digital signal processing and demodulation, this instrument shifts key magnetometer functions from analog electronics to field-programmable gate array based digital processing.
3. **Advanced Digital Magnetic Feedback** – A digital magnetic feedback topology, developed by the PI, for future solar wind monitoring and lunar lander payloads.
4. **Radiation-Tolerant Design** – Prototypes critical instrument subsystems using high-fidelity engineering-grade components, demonstrating functionality in a 100 krad-tolerant design.

The PI, Dr. David Miles of the University of Iowa, secured a flight opportunity aboard the Investigation of Cusp Irregularities-5 (ICI-5bis) sounding rocket flight campaign, launching from Andøya Space, Norway.

By supporting projects like SWIM, HESTO Pathfinder aims to drive innovation in Heliophysics, ensuring novel technologies are ready for infusion into science missions and to contribute to future discoveries.

Image Credit: Trond Abrahamsen/Andøya Space Center

HELIOTECH: Heliophysics Technology Symposium

2024 HELIOPHYSICS TECHNOLOGY SYMPOSIUM
AT NASA'S WALLOPS FLIGHT FACILITY, VA

Day 1 HELIOTECH2024 attendees at NASA's Wallops Flight Facility, September 18, 2024

Credit: NASA/Garon Clark

The second annual HESTO Heliophysics Technology Symposium, **HELIOTECH2024**, was a resounding success, offering a platform for innovation, learning, and collaboration among the Heliophysics community. Held September 2024 as a hybrid event online and at NASA's Wallops Flight Facility in Virginia, the symposium welcomed 100+ in-person attendees and 200+ virtual participants and featured a robust agenda, including technology presentations, interactive learning forums, facility tours, and invaluable opportunities to engage with program leaders. Representatives from NASA's Sounding Rockets, Balloons, and SmallSat/CubeSat suborbital programs participated to guide technologists on aligning their innovations with flight opportunities, and attendees gained insight into proposing their technologies for demonstration and infusion into science missions.

HELIOTECH2024 attendees during a Q&A session with HESTO's Deputy Lead Scientist Eliad Peretz in the NASA's WFF auditorium
Top Left: Joseph Westlake, Director of NASA HQ Heliophysics Division
Middle Left: David Pierce, Center Director, Wallops Flight Facility
Lower Left: Kyle McAllen, HESTO Program Manager
Credits: NASA/Garon Clark

HELIOTECH2024 attendees enjoyed a guided tour of NASA's WFF that provided firsthand views of facilities supporting Heliophysics research
Credits: NASA/Garon Clark | NASA/Chris Fleming

WE LOOK FORWARD TO SEEING YOU

HELIOTECH 2025 SUBORBITAL SYMPOSIUM

NASA HELIOPHYSICS TECHNOLOGY & SUBORBITAL SYMPOSIUM

Visit the HESTO website for updates about HELIOTECH2025, including schedule, location details, and registration information.

In 2025, HESTO's HELIOTECH will collaborate with **NASA's Suborbital Symposium** for a weeklong joint event. To be held September 2025, and hosted in the Washington, DC/Baltimore, MD area, this joint symposium will be aimed at fostering collaboration between technologists and flight Principal Investigators.

The primary objectives of this joint **HELIOTECH2025** and **NASA's Suborbital Symposium** include incentivizing partnerships for flight infusion of matured technologies to increase the application of innovative solutions into flight proposals to advance Heliophysics science. The joint symposium will also provide a forum for technologists to explore rideshare opportunities on science missions for maturation and demonstration of technologies. The preliminary schedule includes dedicated days for Heliophysics technology sessions, collaborative and learning sessions, and Suborbital (Sounding Rockets and Balloons) sessions. Offered as a hybrid event, this joint symposium will continue to accommodate in-person and online participation, ensuring broad participation.

HOSTED IN THE
WASHINGTON DC
CAPITOL AREA

SUBORBITAL PROGRAM

The suborbital program provides a path for advancing the technology readiness levels of future space flight technologies.

Focusing Optics X-ray Solar Imager (FOXSI)
 Juan Camilo Buitrago Casas, UCB/SSL; Lindsay Glesener, Univ of Minnesota;
 Säm Krucker, UCB/SSL foxsi.umn.edu

First launched in 2012, the FOXSI sounding rockets have pioneered applying direct hard x-ray imaging technologies such as grazing-incidence optics from NASA MSFC and solid-state strip detectors from ISAS/JAXA both originally developed for astrophysics to observing the high energy x-ray emission from the Sun.

High Angular Resolution Replicated Hard X-ray Optics

Grazing incidence optics can be fabricated with a variety of different technics. MSFC uses a replication technique whereby a metal form is electroformed onto a precision polished cylindrical mandrel. The full shell optic is then removed from the form. A set of important enhancements to this process includes a deterministic polishing technique using a seven axis CNC optical polishing/form generating machine, improved shell formation and separation, optimized pulse plating for stress reduction, and advanced mandrel/shell release processes.

Microfabricated Pixelated Attenuators (MPAs)

to hard X-rays for each individual pixel.

Solar flares, which are very bright in X-ray bands, emit more low energy (soft) X-rays than high energy (hard) X-rays. To attenuate X-rays but not overwhelm the detector, a filter is typically used to decrease soft X-rays. However, this also removes most, if not all, soft X-rays. MPAs have small holes and thinner regions that let some soft X-rays through in addition

X-ray Optics Collimator

from reaching the detector.

Grazing incidence optics are commonly used to focus X-rays onto a pixelated detector. These optics use two surfaces to reflect and focus X-rays to create an image. However, X-rays that bounce on only one surface may reach the detector and create complex patterns that can confuse the primary image. The FOXI team designed a precision collimator to block these X-rays

The Low-Cost Access to Space (LCAS) program seeks to advance science, as well as advance the development and demonstration of technologies to enable future investigations. Technologies developed through H-TiDeS can be infused into LCAS missions. Highlighted are some technologies developed, infused, and demonstrated through LCAS.

Endurance Sounding Rocket Mission
 Glyn Collinson, NASA's GSFC

sites.wff.nasa.gov/code810/news/story268-47.001%20Endurance.html

Understanding the processes that lead to atmospheric losses is important to understanding how planetary atmospheres evolve over time, including Earth's. The Endurance sounding rocket launched to a ~780 km altitude above Earth's sunlit polar cap from Svalbard to make the first measurement of the weak "ambipolar" electric field generated by Earth's ionosphere. Endurance was the first experiment to measure the very weak electrostatic electric field that pushes ions out of the Earth's atmosphere into space. This discovery would not have been possible without PES, a new plasma spectrometer developed specifically for the mission. Endurance results will help determine the importance of ion escape in this previously unmeasured fundamental property of our planet and aid in a better understanding of what makes Earth habitable

Photoelectron Spectrometer (PES)

PES is a new plasma spectrometer with very high energy resolution. It measures the energy spectra of electrons inflowing and outflowing from planetary ionospheres. It measures two data products every 10 seconds: a standard resolution (15% DE/E) survey between 10 eV and 1 keV and a high resolution (0.5% DE/E) scan anywhere up to 30 eV. PES achieves this performance through a novel combination of two common types of plasma analyzer.

Electrons entering the PES traverse a "Top Hat" electrostatic analyzer (ESA). The ESA provides an initial broad bandpass energy filter to incoming electrons. Electrons then pass through a high-resolution Retarding Potential Analyzer, which is electrically biased to threshold the energy of the electrons that can reach the detector. Electrons are detected by a pair of Channel Electron Multipliers (CEM).

Atmospheric Perturbations around Eclipse Path (APEP)
 Aroh Barjatya, Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University sites.erau.edu/sail/apep

The ionosphere is the boundary between Earth's atmosphere and space. Its dynamics are highly coupled to sunlight, which ionizes the particles that fill the ionosphere. Without sunlight, the ionosphere becomes thinner as particles recombine back into neutral particles. Solar eclipses are a rare opportunity to understand how the ionosphere reacts to a rapid sunset and sunrise and how perturbations travel through the ionosphere.

Positive Ion Probe

The Positive Ion Probe is a highly sensitive miniaturized Langmuir probe instrument developed by the Space and Atmospheric Instrumentation Laboratory at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University. It is capable of conducting high-cadence (5 KHz) distributed relative-ion density measurements from sounding rocket or cubesat platforms. It first flew on a mid-latitude sounding rocket mission, Sporadic-E ElectroDynamics Demonstration (SpEED Demon), which launched from NASA's Wallops Flight Facility in August 2022 and was further developed and flown on APEP. PIP works by maintaining a fixed-bias in the ion saturation region so it is negatively biased with respect to the plasma. This repels electrons, so positive charge is collected on the instrument's conductive surface. Analysis of the collected current allows for high-cadence *in situ* measurements of relative change in ion density. The data are expressed in terms of absolute density only after measurements from other instruments have been considered. A Planar version of PIP suitable for cubesats can weigh as little as 20 grams, including electronics.

High-resolution Coronal Imager solar Flare (Hi-C Flare)
 Sabrina Savage, NASA's MSFC hic.msfc.nasa.gov

The Hi-C Flare campaign provided a unique opportunity to test Hi-C configured for high-temperature observations along with new, flare-optimized instrumentation to probe flare energy release. The Hi-C Flare sounding rocket launched on April 17, 2024, from the Poker Flat Research Range in Alaska. Hi-C Flare was designed to observe a solar flare with a high-resolution, low-noise extreme ultraviolet (12.9 nm) imager (Hi-C 3) and an extreme ultraviolet (EUV) slitless spectrometer (COOL-AID) combined with soft X-ray imaging (SSAXI) and high cadence flux measurements (CAPRI-SUN).

COOronal OverLapogram – Ancillary Imaging Diagnostics (COOL-AID)

The COOL-AID experiment is a slit-less extreme ultra-violet (EUV) spectrograph consisting of a fold mirror, reflective diffraction grating, focus mirror, and charge coupled device (CCD) detector. Without a slit, the spectrograph provides two-dimensional solar images in multiple wavelengths. These appear overlapped on the detector but can be "unfolded" using new software recently demonstrated on data from the Marshall Grazing Incidence X-ray Spectrometer (MaGIXS) sounding rocket experiment.

The flat fold mirror and spherical focus mirror were chosen for their affordability and extremely low figure error and surface roughness. This decision allowed the development effort to focus on the 5000 line/mm blazed sawtooth grating, which was created using interference lithography. The COOL-AID grating is a prototype for the grating in the EUV CME and Coronal Connectivity Observatory (ECCCO), currently in a NASA SMEX Phase A. COOL-AID was designed and built by the Harvard-Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory, a partnering institution on Hi-C Flare.

EARLY CAREER PI SPOTLIGHT

Alex Chartier

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Satellite Auroral Plasma Sounders
22-HFOS22-0003

Dr. Alex Chartier's research focuses on the boundary between Earth's atmosphere and space, crucial due to the proliferation of satellites in LEO. He combines data from various sources with models to understand ionospheric dynamics. Starting in Antarctica in 2017, he began developing radio remote sensing instruments to fill measurement gaps. He has since conducted tests on various platforms, aiming for a remote-sensing ionospheric network constellation. The first space test, Ionospheric Topside Sounding from ISS (ITSI), is scheduled in 2025, with plans for a CubeSat mission. Alex leads the Super Dual Auroral Radar Network (SuperDARN) project at APL and is involved with Active Magnetosphere and Planetary Electrodynamics Response Experiment (AMPERE), using commercial satellite data to detect Birkeland currents.

Robert Clayton

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Development of a miniaturized Double Langmuir
Probe for Small-Sat Platforms | 22-HTIDS22-0018

Dr. Robert Clayton is an early career Research Scientist studying low Earth atmosphere plasma dynamics at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University's Space and Atmospheric Instrumentation Lab (SAIL). He works with SAIL to design, simulate, prototype, and demonstrate a variety of low size-weight-and-power (SWaP) instrumentation for use on high-altitude balloons, sub-orbital sounding rockets, orbital satellites, and the upcoming Escape and Plasma Acceleration and Dynamics Explorers (EscaPADE) Mars mission. This instrumentation is targeted toward studying plasma density, temperature, and potential through the use of sweeping and fixed voltage Langmuir probes. Development and testing is performed using SAIL's in-house Plasma Chamber facilities, simulating ionosphere-like conditions prior to in situ deployment.

Feiyu Li

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Scaling Studies of Seeded Alfvén Wave Parametric
Decay Instability in the Lab | 22-HTIDS22-0019

Dr. Feiyu Li is a Research Scientist at the New Mexico Consortium (NMC), Los Alamos, NM. He received his PhD in Plasma Physics from Shanghai Jiao Tong University. Before joining the NMC, he worked as a postdoc researcher at the University of Strathclyde, UK, and the Los Alamos National Lab. Dr. Li's research interests primarily focus on computational, theoretical, and experimental modeling of plasma processes with applications to laser plasma accelerators, attosecond metrology, space science, and fusion energy. His current projects involve experimental and computational study of nonlinear Alfvén waves based on the Large Plasma Device at UCLA and their implications to prominent Heliophysical phenomena, such as solar coronal heating and solar wind acceleration.

Mihailo Martinović

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Measuring Plasma Parameters and Waves in the
Ionosphere of Earth | 22-HTIDS22-0013

Dr. Mihailo Martinović is a Researcher at the University of Arizona and obtained his PhD at the Paris Observatory in 2016. He is PI of the Waves, Instabilities, and Noise Spectrometer (WINS) instrument to measure electric field fluctuations in Earth's ionosphere, and Co-I on the Radio and Plasma Waves (RPW) instrument on the European Space Agency's Solar Orbiter mission. His research interests span questions of solar wind heating and acceleration, and he is PI of multiple research programs to develop space instrumentation for Quasi-Thermal Noise (QTN) spectroscopy observations. He developed and maintains a Stability Analysis Vitalizing Instability Classification Machine Learning algorithm used to map electromagnetic waves in solar wind plasma.

Rachael Filwett

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LabOratory for the Behavior of the Slot Region
(LOBSTR) | 21-HFOS21-0002

Dr. Rachael Filwett is an Assistant Professor of Physics at Montana State University. She received her BS from Valparaiso University and her MS and PhD from the University of San Antonio in the joint program with the Southwest Research Institute. She is interested in energetic particle dynamics, particularly ions originating at the Sun, and how magnetic field transport modifies particle behavior. To gain new insights into the physics behind these particles, she is involved in both mission and instrumentation development. She is Principal Investigator of LOBSTR, a Heliophysics Flight Opportunity Study that looks to understand the particle dynamics in the slot region between Earth's two radiation belts.

Mary Knapp

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Space Weather Impact on Planetary Emissions
(SWIPE) | 22-HFOS22-0002

Dr. Mary Knapp is a research scientist at MIT Haystack Observatory. She received her BS in Aerospace Engineering in 2011 and PhD in Planetary Science in 2018 at MIT. Her research focus is detection and characterization of exoplanetary magnetic fields via low frequency radio emission. She currently is a NASA Innovative Advanced Concepts Fellow for the Great Observatory for Long Wavelengths (GO-LoW). Her additional research interests include development of small spacecraft missions and instruments for Heliophysics, astronomy, and planetary science. She served as ASTERIA CubeSat project scientist since 2010, through launch and operations until end of mission, and is currently deputy PI for the AERO-VISTA twin CubeSat mission to study Earth's auroral radio emission.

Majd Mayyasi

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High-Resolution Spectrograph in Lyman- α (HIRSL) |
22-HTIDS22-0007

Dr. Majd Mayyasi is a senior research scientist at the Center for Space Physics at Boston University (BU). She holds a BS in Computer Engineering, a BS in Physics and Mathematics, and a PhD in Astronomy. Her research interests include understanding Martian atmosphere evolution and loss, water loss from planets and comets, and how the interplanetary medium interacts with the interstellar medium. She is currently building a high resolution UV spectrograph prototype at BU. Majd also serves as an IPA with NASA, runs the Mars Data Analysis Program, and works with the Planetary Exploration Science Technology Office. When not working, Majd enjoys being in nature, hand drumming, martial arts, and learning Japanese.

Mykhaylo Shumko

mike.shumko@jhuapl.edu | The Loss Through
Auroral Microburst Pulsations Satellite (LAMPsat)
Flight Opportunity Study | 22-HFOS22-0007

Dr. Mykhaylo (Mike) Shumko is a postdoctoral fellow at Johns Hopkins University's Applied Physics Laboratory. His research interests include advancing our understanding of the ionosphere, inner magnetosphere, and magnetotail environments. He studies energetic particles streaming into Earth's atmosphere from near-Earth space. While the lower energy particles produce the stunning displays of the aurora, the higher energy particles are a radiation hazard to our presence in space. He is PI of the Loss through Auroral Microburst Pulsations (LAMPsat) concept, which will advance our understanding of the impact of these low- and high-altitude particles. From low Earth orbit, this novel mission will unravel the mystery of when the beautiful auroral light comes with hazardous electrons.

Justin H. Lee

Justin.H.Lee@aero.org
Miniaturized Charging Mitigation Shell Instrument
for Cold Plasma | 22-HTIDS22-0023

Dr. Justin H. Lee is a research scientist whose work has included technology and instrument development, as well as flight experiments. His experiments have flown on a variety of platforms, including nano-satellites and small high-altitude balloons, and he continues to investigate the returned in-flight data. Dr. Lee has interest in low-energy plasma composition and its effects on electromagnetic waves in Earth's magnetospheric plasma, interpreting on-orbit phenomena data from instruments hosted on NASA's MMS and THEMIS. He continues to draw on experience with nanosatellite-hosted experiments and the exploitation of measurements from on-orbit instruments to motivate ongoing development of miniaturized instrument technologies that support future progress leveraging low size, weight, and power platforms.

Solène Lejosne

solene@berkeley.edu | Development of
Grotifer: a CubeSat for Three-Dimensional Electric
Field Measurements | 21-HTIDS21-0002

Dr. Solène Lejosne is an Associate Researcher at the Space Sciences Laboratory of the University of California, Berkeley. She is a graduate of École Polytechnique (engineering cycle) and Institut Supérieur de l'Aéronautique et de l'Espace (ISAE-SUPAERO), and she received her PhD in Space Physics from the University of Toulouse, France. She conducts research on a variety of research projects (theory, modeling, field, and particle data analysis), mainly focused on energetic particle transport in the inner magnetosphere, including radiation belt radial transport and radial diffusion. She is Principal Investigator of the Grotifer project, a NASA HTIDEs effort with the objective of developing a new design for the double-probe electric field instrument.

Samuel Tun Beltran

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An Imaging Polarimeter for Hydrogen Lyman- α |
21-HTIDS21-0010

Dr. Samuel Tun earned his PhD from the New Jersey Institute of Technology, specializing in solar radio observations. He joined the Naval Research Laboratory as a National Research Council postdoctoral fellow, continuing his radio studies and serving as Assembly, Integration, and Testing (AIT) lead for the VERY high angular Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (VERIS) and Very high Angular resolution ULtraviolet Telescope (VAULT) sounding rockets. He also assisted with characterizing the Solar Orbiter Heliospheric Imager (SoloHI) detector. Dr. Tun is PI for the HELium Resonance Scatter in the Corona and HELiosphere (HERSCHEL) sounding rocket and is developing on-chip polarizers under NASA's HFORT program. He was AIT and detector lead on UltraViolet Solar Coronagraph and is currently detector lead for the Extreme UltraViolet Solar Telescope.

Xiaojia Zhang

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High-Frequency Magnetic Loop for Heliophysics
Exploration | 21-HTIDS21-0004

Dr. Xiaojia Zhang is an associate professor in the Department of Physics, University of Texas (UT) at Dallas. She received her BA in Space Physics from Peking University and PhD in Geophysics and Space Physics from University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA). Before joining UT Dallas, she worked as an associate researcher at UCLA. Her research focuses on energetic particle dynamics in Earth's magnetosphere and the effects of particle precipitation on Earth's atmosphere, with efforts to develop innovative, low-cost space instrumentation for monitoring space weather. Dr. Zhang led development of the first miniaturized high-frequency magnetic field sensor in the US, HFLoop, designed for 3D radio burst early detection, exploration, and tracking on small satellite platforms.

STUDENT TECHNOLOGISTS

HESTO is tasked with supporting the maturation of Heliophysics Technology investments and facilitating their infusion into future spaceflight missions. To further this goal, HESTO is working to create a dynamic, interactive science and technology community of current and future thinkers striving to develop tomorrow's solutions to our biggest Heliophysics questions. HESTO actively engages and encourages student technologists toward career paths that develop our future research, technology, and mission principal investigators. HESTO supports:

Discovery through transformative technological advancements fueled by a community that includes current experts along with those who will be the future drivers of technology and science discovery.

Opportunity for students at all education levels – high school, undergraduate, graduate, and post-doctoral – as well as for cross-cutting technology teams to participate in events that bring together current principal investigators with future scientists and technologists, as well as multidisciplinary viewpoints from outside the established Heliophysics community.

Collaboration to foster cooperation and information sharing, catalyzing collaborative technological advancement between scientific disciplines, technology development pathways, and current and future scientists and technologists.

AUBURN UNIVERSITY

- * Will Teague PHYSICS
- * Tithi Patel AEROSPACE
- ◆ Saylor Jordan AEROSPACE
- ◆ Benjamin Colvett AEROSPACE
- ◆ Claire Brandon AEROSPACE
- ◆ Jordan Jett AEROSPACE
- * Rahul Banka ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES

BOSTON UNIVERSITY

- * Patrick Lierle ASTRONOMY
- ❖ Ashley Gomez ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING

CATONSVILLE HIGH SCHOOL

- Teagan Frenkel PHYSICS/MATH

COLORADO STATE UNIVERSITY

- ❖ Seth Thompson MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

DARTMOUTH COLLEGE

- ❖ Ben Hogan AEROSPACE ENGINEERING SCIENCES

EMBRY-RIDDLE AERONAUTICAL UNIVERSITY

- ◆ Johnathan Bizzano ENGINEERING PHYSICS

HARVARD UNIVERSITY

- ❖ Sophia Sánchez-Maes ASTROPHYSICS

MICHIGAN STATE UNIVERSITY

- ◆ David Benkes-Toth MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

NORTHERN BURLINGTON REGIONAL COUNTY H.S.

- Alma Alex GENERAL STUDIES

PRINCETON UNIVERSITY

- * Kendra Bergstedt ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Rachel Wang ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Adam Robbins ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Josh Pawlak ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Steve Majeski ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES

STANFORD UNIVERSITY

- * Spencer Bell MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

UNIVERSITY OF ARIZONA

- ◆ Sarina Blanchard MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
- ◆ Kane Mattison AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Ahmad Qureshi SOFTWARE ENGINEERING / ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING
- ◆ Ryan McDermott ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING

UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA SAN DIEGO

- * Izzy Thomas ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES

UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, BERKELEY

- ◆ Tatsuyoshi Kurumiya MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
- ◆ Joshua Zhou EECS & APPLIED MATH
- ◆ Van Khoi Vu MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
- ◆ Orion Niklaus V MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, DAVIS

- * Humphry Chen PHOTONICS

UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, LOS ANGELES

- * Bennett Ji AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Alissa Tong AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Axel Della Porta MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
- * Samir Mallya MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
- ◆ Sijie Peng ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING
- * Dewanshi Roy ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING
- * Elias Forey ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING
- ❖ Ava Asmani ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING
- ❖ Ethan Tsai GEOPHYSICS/SPACE PHYSICS
- * Shiyu Xia ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING

UNIVERSITY OF COLORADO BOULDER

- ◆ Lauren Christenson AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Justin Astalos AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ❖ Declan O'Brien AEROSPACE ENGINEERING SCIENCES
- ❖ Juliana Barstow ASTROPHYSICS
- * Tyler Bishop ASTROPHYSICAL & PLANETARY SCIENCES
- ◆ Jennifer Cuevas-Morales AEROSPACE ENGINEERING SCIENCES

UNIVERSITY OF IOWA

- ◆ Connor Hogan MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
- ◆ Max Finch COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
- ◆ Sam Witte ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING
- ◆ Tino Smith ASTRONOMY, PHYSICS, MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
- * Jessica Mondoskin PHYSICS WITH ASTRONOMY
- * Olivia Jones PHYSICS WITH ASTRONOMY
- * Robert Broadfoot PHYSICS WITH ASTRONOMY
- * Kenton Greene PHYSICS WITH ASTRONOMY
- * Allison Flores ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING
- ❖ Matthew Blandin SPACE PHYSICS

UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND, BALTIMORE COUNTY

- ◆ Lucas Cunningham COMPUTER SCIENCE

UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND, COLLEGE PARK

- ❖ Emma Mirizio ASTRONOMY
- ◆ Danjing Chen MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
- * Kyle Hrenyo PLASMA PHYSICS

UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN

- ❖ Shirsh Soni
- ❖ Tsige Atilaw
- ❖ Matti Ala-Lahti
- * Lawanya Awasthi
- ❖ Tyler Eddy SPACE PHYSICS
- ❖ Alex Hoffmann SPACE SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
- ❖ Jhanene Heying-Melendrez APPLIED PHYSICS
- ❖ Burak Ay SPACE SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
- * Julio Vatta ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING
- * Surya Kalluri SPACE SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
- ◆ Jennifer Wang ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING
- ◆ Jake Stollman AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Jacob Klinger AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Mya Enzer SPACE SCIENCES AND ENGINEERING

UNIVERSITY OF NEW HAMPSHIRE

- ❖ Lance Davis PHYSICS

UNIVERSITY OF TOKYO

- * Mizuki Tanaka ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES
- * Yuka Doke ASTROPHYSICAL SCIENCES

UNIVERSITY OF WISCONSIN-MILWAUKEE

- ◆ Emma Schultz-Stachnik PHYSICS

VANDERBILT UNIVERSITY

- ❖ Crisel Suarez PHYSICS/ASTROPHYSICS

VIRGINIA TECH

- * Nicholas Jones AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- * Neha Chinthapatla AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- * Michael Punaro ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING
- ◆ Allison Hai AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Joshua Smith AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Nathan Huh AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ❖ Jessica Brooks COMPUTER SCIENCE
- ❖ Sowmya Lakshmi Muthurangan AEROSPACE ENGINEERING
- ◆ Thomas Soll Kang AEROSPACE ENGINEERING

WEST VIRGINIA UNIVERSITY

- ❖ Justin Bowman PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY
- ◆ Justin Riggs PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY

KEY

- High School
- * Graduate
- ◆ Undergraduate
- ❖ PhD/PostDoc

*Does not include all student participants from 2024

HELIOPHYSICS TECHNOLOGY PROGRAM ANALYSIS GROUP

Greetings from H-TPAG! The Heliophysics Technology Program Analysis Group (H-TPAG) is a community-based interdisciplinary forum for soliciting and coordinating community analysis and input in support of Heliophysics Technology Program (HTP) objectives.

H-TPAG was formed to enable direct and regular communication between NASA and the Heliophysics community and to enable dialogue within the Heliophysics community toward providing science, technology, and programmatic input to NASA's Heliophysics Division (HPD).

In 2024, H-TPAG conducted a survey of current and past Heliophysics Technology PIs to analyze the adequacy of technology development opportunities in Heliophysics and the success of the funded technology projects managed by HESTO. This provided a baseline for the community and HPD. The results of this survey are available on the HESTO website (hesto.smce.nasa.gov/technology-assessment-group/).

H-TPAG looks forward to engaging with the community and contributing to HESTO's goal of establishing a vibrant community where enhanced interactions and collaborations lead to advancements in Heliophysics science. With the release of the 2024 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics, H-TPAG looks forward to engaging with the community to support HPD in aligning technology solicitations and funding with the science goals of the next decade and beyond and developing innovative solutions for maturation and infusion of developed technologies.

All community members are encouraged to participate in H-TPAG. The group is led by members of the Heliophysics community, and leadership is rotated every three years to invigorate and support maximum engagement with and for the community. In 2025, H-TPAG will host its first public event to further engage the Heliophysics technology community.

H-TPAG Committee Co-Chair: Dr. Aroh Barjatya is Professor of Engineering Physics at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University and Director of its Space and Atmospheric Instrumentation Laboratory. He is PI/Co-I on three sounding rocket missions, PI/Co-I on two H-TiDeS instrument development projects, and Co-I/instrument PI on the ESCAPE mission, contributing a Langmuir probe suite.

H-TPAG Committee Co-Chair: Dr. Phyllis Whittlesey is a Research Scientist and Deputy Associate Director of Solar and Heliophysics at University of California, Berkeley/SSL. She is a Co-I/Instrument Scientist for the Parker Solar Probe SPAN-E instruments/PI of SPAN-I, PI for HelioSwarm Student Collaboration Electron Electrostatic Spectrograph, and Instrument Lead for the ESCAPE Electrostatic Analyzer.

H-TPAG Committee Member: Dr. Matina Gkioulidou is a space physicist at the Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Laboratory. She is a Co-I and Project Scientist of NASA's IMAP mission and led development of the IMAP ENA camera. She is the Deputy Instrument Scientist for the JENI instrument on ESA's JUICE mission. She was also Co-I for RBSPICE on NASA's Van Allen Probes.

H-TPAG Committee Member: Dr. Katherine Goodrich is an Assistant Professor at West Virginia University. Her research focuses on the microphysics of collisionless shocks in space, structures arising from plasma turbulence, and wave-particle interactions. She develops instrumentation and data analysis techniques to measure electric fields in space and is a Co-I on NASA's Parker Solar Probe and MMS missions.

H-TPAG Committee Member: Dr. Stefano Livi is an Institute Scientist at Southwest Research Institute. He has served as Co-I on a variety of missions, including Phobos, Polar, Cassini, Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO), Rosetta, and Geotail. He is PI of the Strofio sensor on ESA's BepiColombo mission, which will study Mercury's tenuous exosphere. He is also PI of the Solar Orbiter's HIS instrument.

H-TPAG Committee Member: Dr. Carlos Maldonado is a member of the Space Science and Applications Group at the Los Alamos National Laboratory. He is Project Lead of the ESRA cubesat mission, a Co-I on NASA's Interstellar Mapping and Acceleration Probe (IMAP) mission, and PI of a NASA H-TiDeS award to develop a novel, cubesat-compatible, compact ion mass spectrometer capable of high mass resolution.

H-TPAG Committee Member: Dr. David Miles is an F Wendell Miller Associate Professor in the Department of Physics and Astronomy at the University of Iowa. He is PI of NASA's TRACERS mission and the MAGIC technology demonstration. He has also provided fluxgate magnetometers for Ex-Alt-1 and multiple sounding rocket missions.

GET INVOLVED IN H-TPAG

Join the H-TPAG Slack Group

Join the H-TPAG Google Group

LOOKING AHEAD

As this issue of our annual Heliophysics Technology Report demonstrates, 2024 has been a remarkable year of breakthroughs and collaboration. Our efforts have laid a solid foundation for an even more ambitious and inspiring year ahead in 2025.

We are thrilled to have expanded our team with the addition of a new Deputy Lead Scientist, further strengthening our capacity to innovate and advance Heliophysics. Our website continues to evolve as a hub for news about our technology investments and upcoming initiatives. We encourage you to visit it regularly to stay informed and engaged.

The 2024 Heliophysics Technology Symposium (HELIOTECH) was a resounding success, fostering invaluable networking, learning, and collaboration. Building on this momentum, we are excited to announce the HELIOTECH2025 Symposium, which will take place September 2025 in the Washington, DC/Baltimore, MD area. HELIOTECH2025 will feature contributions across the entire Heliophysics community, broadening the scope of our shared knowledge and innovation. Watch for announcements via email and HESTO's website – we look forward to seeing you there!

In alignment with the NASA Science Mission Directorate dual-anonymous peer review (DAPR) process, HESTO will use DAPR to solicit and evaluate ROSES 2025 Heliophysics Technology Program solicitations. To prepare prospective PIs, we will provide comprehensive guidance on our website.

The Heliophysics Technology and Program Analysis Group (H-TPAG) executive committee is now fully staffed, and under the visionary leadership of Professor Barjatya of Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University and Dr. Whittlesey of the University of California, Berkeley, conducted a pivotal survey to gather input from our technology PIs. These insights will help refine our technology solicitations, achieve a balanced portfolio, and enhance HESTO's effectiveness.

In 2024, HESTO reached an exciting milestone with the selection of its first Pathfinder project. HESTO Pathfinder's aim is to mature key technology investments through flight. This marks the beginning of a new era of possibilities, and we look forward to providing additional Pathfinder opportunities in 2025.

Finally, release of the 2024 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics represents a transformative moment for our community. We are eager to build upon this roadmap to guide our technology investments, to take advantage of emerging new technologies, and enable groundbreaking Heliophysics science for the next decade and beyond.

As we close out 2024, we invite you to join us in embracing the challenges that lie ahead. Together, we will push the boundaries of what is possible, empowering the Heliophysics community to achieve extraordinary advancements in understanding our Sun and its impact on our solar system. Thank you for your continued partnership and dedication to this vital mission.

2024

- FEB — 2023 Annual Report Released
ROSES-2024 H-TiDeS & H-FOS Solicitation Announcement
- WINTER — H-TPAG Charter Release
- SPRING — H-TPAG Executive Committee Constituted
- JUN — First H-TPAG Executive Committee Meeting
- SUMMER — Pathfinder Selection
- AUG — H-TPAG Survey of Heliophysics Technology Program
ROSES-2024 H-TiDeS & H-FOS Proposals Due
- SEP — HELIOTECH 2024
- DEC — 2024 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics Released
American Geophysical Union (AGU) Meeting

2025

- JAN — ROSES-2024 H-TiDeS & H-FOS Selections
- MAR — 2024 Annual Report Released
ROSES-2025 H-TiDeS & H-FOS Released
- SPRING — H-TPAG Meeting
Form Decadal Tech Working Group
- AUG — ROSES-2024 H-TiDeS & H-FOS Proposals Due
- SEP — HELIOTECH 2025
- FALL — H-TPAG Meeting
- DEC — American Geophysical Union (AGU) Meeting

2026

- JAN — ROSES-2025 H-TiDeS & H-FOS Selections
- FEB — 2025 Annual Report Released
ROSES-2026 H-TiDeS & H-FOS Released

About the Cover

HESTO's mission is to foster connections between scientific exploration and technology innovation centered on the Sun. The 2024 Heliophysics Technology Annual Report cover art is inspired by this mission and Heliophysics Big Year events, including the total solar eclipse on April 8, 2024. The artist's concept began in the moment of totality, where the awesome power and importance of the Sun becomes even more starkly evident through its absence. The clouds streaming around the Sun represent the energy of information flowing through the Heliophysics community and the circuitry elements represent the network of individuals and institutions in the community, highlighting the potential of inter-connection. Illustration Credit: NASA/Christa Harmon

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